

Modified Hierarchical Modulation for Hybrid RF-FSO Satellite Communication

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Abstract—This paper proposes a Modified Hierarchical Modulation (MHM) technique implemented over a Hybrid Radio Frequency-Free-Space Optical (RF-FSO) satellite system. At the transmitter, a data block with a fixed length N is divided into two streams—the high-priority (HP) stream and the low-priority (LP) stream. The HP stream contains n bits and is transmitted over the RF link, while the LP stream contains m bits and is transmitted over the FSO link. At the receiver, the HP stream is demodulated and used as an a priori information to demodulate the LP stream. We show that this system performs better in terms of Bit-Error Rate (BER) over different levels of Signal-to-Noise Ratio (SNR) and elevation angles compared to classical combining schemes such as Maximal Ratio Combining (MRC). The reported Monte Carlo simulations show that for an operational range of SNR, the proposed technique increases the 0.01 data rate percentile a 14.9%.

Index Terms—hybrid RF-FSO, free-space optics, satellite communications, hierarchical modulation

I. INTRODUCTION

The ever-increasing demand for higher data rate satellite communication has pushed the existing Radio Frequency (RF) communication infrastructure to capacity crunch and driven the integration of Free-Space Optical (FSO) communications due to its higher capacity [1]. Despite the promising high data rate achieved through FSO communication, it faces challenges such as severe availability and reliability due to its susceptibility to weather effects like fog, rain, snow and clouds in the atmosphere, compared to RF links. Nonetheless, even though RF communication is more robust under these conditions, it still has limited available bandwidth for some applications such as the download of Earth observation data; thus, FSO communication is still a good solution to certain applications [2]. Indeed, in recent times, space agencies have grown interested in exploring using the optical band for satellite transmission, such as the European Space Agency’s ScyLight (SeCure and Laser communication Technology, pronounced “skylight”) [3] and Space Development Agency’s project collaboration with Mynaric [4].

This underwork was supported by the Catalan government through the Institució Catalana de Recerca i Estudis Avançats (ICREA) Grant, and in part, by the Agència Estatal de Investigació, Ministerio de Ciencia e Innovación funded by MCIN/AEI/ 10.13039/501100011033 through the R+D+i Project Grant IRENE PID2020-115323RB-C31, by the Catalan government through the project SGR-Cat 2021-01207

As a matter of fact, current commercial FSO solutions have a tremendous capacity reaching hundreds of gigabits per second in clear sky conditions. However, the overall system dimensioning generally relies on a backup RF link medium data-rate solution as a supporting alternative when the optical suffers an outage. This RF-FSO switching is not seamless and it impacts the end-to-end connectivity. In this context, combining RF and FSO links becomes instrumental for efficient space-to-Earth and Earth-to-space communications in an unnoticed fashion for the final user. Clearly, whenever we promote a coordinated physical layer transmission, symbol periods shall be equal for both links leading to a reduction of the FSO capacity at expenses of a high overall reliability and seamless switching.

Several combining schemes have been proposed to combine the signals from both links in the terrestrial domain. The most popular ones are Maximal Ratio Combining (MRC) and Selective Combining (SC) [5]. In [6], both RF and FSO links are assumed to have synchronous symbol periods and both are modulated using Phase Shift (PSK) at the transmitter and the receiver electrically combines them. In [7], an adaptive combining scheme is used wherein MRC is implemented when the instantaneous Signal-to-Noise Ratio (SNR) of the FSO link has dropped below the pre-defined threshold. In all the above works, it is imposed that the same signal is transmitted by both interfaces which limits the end-to-end adaptability as the links may have a disparity of channel quality values.

In satellite communications, the atmosphere has distinct effects on the FSO and RF signals, thus having different modulation orders in both links becomes pivotal to take advantage of the benefits of both solutions. In this regard, and with the aim of considering the overall system resilience, we revisit the concept of Hierarchical Modulation (HM), a two-stream modulation technique used in single transmitter-to-receiver links to prevent reception breakdown during poor SNR conditions [8]. In typical HM, instead of directly modulating a fixed length data block, it is divided into two streams and designated as high-priority (HP) and low-priority (LP) then modulated using Quadrature Phase Shift Keying (QPSK) and Quadrature Amplitude Modulation (QAM) respectively. The HP stream determines which quadrant of the constellation

Fig. 1: System Diagram of Modified Hierarchical Modulation

diagram the data block should be located, while the LP stream locates where within that quadrant the data block should be mapped, the streams are added then transmitted over a single link, then decomposed at the receiver to form a bigger QAM constellation. In our proposed technique, we modified HM in a manner that it can be applied to a Hybrid RF-FSO link, where the HP and LP streams are sent over the RF and FSO links respectively.

Numerical validation uses a compound channel model for RF and FSO links in low Earth orbit (LEO) systems. These systems generally show different channel conditions depending on the elevation angle. Indeed, poor channel conditions show up in low elevation angles as within the slant path distorting elements appear while in high elevation angles, it generally has good channel quality. We create an overall channel model that is used to evaluate the system considering the pass of the LEO satellite, proving performance values for the end-to-end system.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows: In Section II, the proposed technique is thoroughly described. In Section III, the channel models used to characterize the links are provided, and in Section IV, the results and discussion are shown. And finally, the paper is concluded in Section V.

II. SYSTEM MODEL

This section details the modulation techniques used for both RF and FSO signals at the transmitter, the decoding and combining schemes used at the receiver, to implement the Modified Hierarchical Modulation (MHM) technique. The system considered contains i) a bit stream selector that designates the prioritization of the streams, ii) a transmitter with a pair of RF and laser antennas with their respective modulators; and iii) a receiver with the corresponding antennas, detector and demodulators, as shown in Fig. 1.

Hierarchical Modulation is a technique that divides the information bits into two and modulates them separately. It lowers the modulation indices, which in effect, makes the system more robust on low SNR conditions. It is typically

Fig. 2: Formation of the Constellation Diagram of Modified Hierarchical Modulation

implemented on single links, where the modulated HP and LP streams are added using an energy-sharing mechanism before being sent over the channel. However, in a Hybrid RF-FSO system, there are two available links to exploit; therefore, it is no longer needed to perform such energy sharing mechanism to add the HP and LP symbols as they can be transmitted over the two links simultaneously. Furthermore, since it is no longer needed to add the two symbols, it gives more freedom to use other modulation techniques such as Amplitude Shift Keying (ASK) and Frequency Shift Keying (FSK). Taking into account these new premises and that the RF signal is more robust from channel impairments than FSO in non-terrestrial communications, modifications were introduced such that the HP and the LP streams are sent over the RF and FSO links respectively.

A. Modified Hierarchical Modulation

In the Modified Hierarchical Modulation, the data block with fixed length N is compartmentalized to form the HP and LP streams. the HP stream contains the first n bits and are modulated using either FSK, ASK or QAM, then sent over the RF link, while the LP stream contains the remaining m bits and are modulated using QAM, then sent over the FSO link. At the receiver, the received RF symbol is used to obtain the first n bits and used to select which quadrant the data block shall be located. Then, within that quadrant, the FSO symbol is demapped to determine the exact point to obtain the remaining bits.

As an example, assume that we have a data block of '100010', the HP stream is '10' and can be modulated using QPSK, and the LP stream would be '0010' and modulated using 16-QAM. In comparison to directly modulating the 6-bit stream using 64-QAM, the SNR requirement to properly demodulate the received would be lower. This mapping is shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 3: System performance of an FSO-only link, Maximal Ratio Combining, and Modified Hierarchical Modulation, in terms of Bit Error Rate (x marks denote numerical simulation results), Throughput and Outage Probability, over an AWGN channel

B. Combining Schemes

Several diversity combining schemes can be employed for hybrid RF-FSO systems. The most utilized ones are MRC and SC, where the SNRs of the two links are considered. For the case of MRC, the system SNR is the sum of the SNRs of the two links, Hence the output SNR is given by $SNR_{MRC} = SNR_{RF} + SNR_{FSO}$, and the resulting data is the ratioed sum of the two demodulated data. Whereas, for the case of SC, the system SNR is the best SNR among the two links, hence the output SNR is given by $SNR_{SC} = \max(SNR_{RF}, SNR_{FSO})$, and the output data is the output of the link with better SNR. These schemes can only be implemented by transmitting completely identical information, i.e., same bits and modulation techniques, on the RF and FSO links.

The proposed system has the freedom of transmitting non-identical set of modulated signals over two links respectively. At the receiver, as discussed from the previous subsection, the “combining scheme” for the system is based on the methodical demodulation of the data where the RF signal is an a priori information of the FSO signal. I.e., the output of the RF detection helps decide the demapping of the symbols of the FSO. On this note, it is highly regarded that the proposed system should have a good condition for the RF link. For comparison, we numerically simulate the system and we use a single unsupported FSO link as benchmark to assess the system’s performance.

C. Bit Error Rate (BER) and Throughput

Despite the RF and FSO streams being transmitted over separate links, the RF bits serve as a priori information for the FSO bits, hence the bit probability of error of the FSO, $P_{b,FSO}$, is dependent on the bit probability of error of the RF, $P_{b,RF}$. Therefore, the overall bit probability of error of MHM, $P_{b,MHM}$, is a function of the bit probability of errors of each modulation layer, $P_{b,RF}$ and $P_{b,FSO}$, and it can be expressed as:

$$P_{b,MHM} = \frac{n}{N} \cdot (P_{b,RF}) + \frac{m}{N} \cdot (1 - (1 - P_{b,RF})(1 - P_{b,FSO})). \quad (1)$$

The bit probability of error of each modulation layer can be obtained by averaging the bit probability of errors of the individual bits of the symbols with length $\log_2 M$. In an AWGN channel, the probability that the n -th bit is in error can be expressed using the closed form expression [9]:

$$P_b(n) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{M}} \sum_{i=0}^{(1-2^{-n})\sqrt{M}-1} \left\{ (-1)^{\lfloor \frac{i \cdot 2^{n-1}}{\sqrt{M}} \rfloor} \cdot \left(2^{n-1} - \left\lfloor \frac{i \cdot 2^{n-1}}{\sqrt{M}} + \frac{1}{2} \right\rfloor \right) \cdot \operatorname{erfc} \left((2i+1) \sqrt{\frac{2 \log_2 M \cdot SNR}{2(M-1)}} \right) \right\}, \quad (2)$$

thus the overall probability of error obtained by averaging the probability of errors of the individual bits of an M-QAM symbol is expressed as:

$$P_b = \frac{1}{\log_2 \sqrt{M}} \sum_{n=1}^{\log_2 \sqrt{M}} P_b(n). \quad (3)$$

where E_b/N_0 is the normalized SNR, or SNR per bit. But when atmospheric channel are being considered, the distinct atmospheric effects on the signals that are modelled using different distributions must also be considered.

For the overall throughput, it is obtained as the sum of the throughputs of the two links, given as:

$$\text{Throughput} = \frac{1}{T_{\text{symbol}}} \left(n \cdot (1 - P_{b,RF}) + m \cdot (1 - (1 - P_{b,RF})(1 - P_{b,FSO})) \right), \quad (4)$$

where T_{symbol} is the symbol period assumed to be the same for both links. As mentioned before, this required synchronicity will preclude the usage of the FSO full potential capacity as its

bandwidth is much higher than the RF link. On the contrary, the proposed approach will support a unified physical layer transmission which enhances the resiliency and it does not have the need for switching mechanisms.

The BER and throughput performance of MHM, MRC, and FSO-only (assumed to be selected by SC) over an AWGN channel at different SNR levels are shown in Fig. 3, including the Outage Probability that the system will fail at 0.001 BER, which is the standard for current communication systems. As it can be observed, the proposed MHM outperforms the current approaches. In the proposed QPSK-in-64-QAM model, despite the number of transmitted bits is the same, it is observable the gain in terms of uncoded BER. The symbol period is assumed to be 1 nanosecond.

In order to further validate our proposed RF-FSO combining scheme, we perform an evaluation over a LEO system. For that, we consolidate RF and FSO channel models and we create the compound channel over different elevation angles as described in the next Section.

III. CHANNEL MODELS

In this section, we discuss the channel models used to characterize both the free-space optic channel and the radio frequency channel.

A. Free-Space Optic Channel

For the FSO link, the received signals can be expressed as

$$y_{FSO}(t) = \mu I(t)x_{FSO}(t) + n_{FSO}(t), \quad (5)$$

where μ is the photodiode responsivity and $I(t)$ is the irradiance of the signal, and $n_{FSO}(t)$ is the optical Gaussian noise. Irradiance is a random fluctuation as product of independent random variables, which arise from large-scale and small-scale turbulent eddies that are present in the free-space channel. Its Probability Density Function (PDF) can be modelled using the Gamma-Gamma distribution [10]

$$p(I) = \frac{2(\alpha\beta)^{\frac{(\alpha+\beta)}{2}}}{\Gamma(\alpha)\Gamma(\beta)} I^{\frac{(\alpha+\beta)}{4}-1} K_{\alpha-\beta}\left(2\sqrt{\alpha\beta}I\right), I > 0 \quad (6)$$

where $\Gamma(\cdot)$ is the Gamma function, $K(\cdot)$ is the modified Bessel function of the second kind, and, α and β parameters are related to the large-scale and small-scale scintillations respectively. In order to compute the values of α and β parameters, it must first be obtained the atmospheric refractive index, C_n^2 , and the scintillation index, δ^2 .

The refractive index of a medium describes how light refracts as it passes through it. According to the Hufnagel-Valley (H-V) atmospheric model [11], the refractive index of any point in the atmosphere, C_n^2 , is a function of the altitude, h , considering the wind speed, v , and the nominal refractive index at the ground, A . Thus,

$$C_n^2(h) = 5.94 \times 10^{-53} (v/27)^2 h^{10} e^{-h/1000} + 2.7 \times 10^{-16} e^{-h/1500} + A e^{-h/100}, \quad (7)$$

where the assumption is $v = 21$ m/s and $A = 1.7 \times 10^{-14} \text{ m}^{-2/3}$ for low-wind nighttime, and $v = 57$ m/s and $A = 2.75 \times 10^{-14} \text{ m}^{-2/3}$ for high-wind daytime..

After obtaining the refractive index, the scintillation index, δ^2 , can now be computed as it is a function of the former. The scintillation index describes the strength and weakness of perturbations throughout a propagation path with length, d . In a horizontal path, the scintillation index can simply be given by, $\delta_{Ry}^2 = 1.23 C_n^2 k^{7/6} d^{11/6}$, also known as the Rytov variance, where the wave number, $k = 2\pi/\lambda$. However, for a slant link such as in satellite communication, the uplink or downlink signal passes through the atmosphere, thus, the channel it propagates through has varying values of refractive indices. Therefore, the Rytov variance should be calculated by considering the integration of all the refractive indices of the points where the signal passed through. Thus, the expression for the scintillation index needs to be modified into a function that includes satellite altitude, H and elevation angle, θ [12].

$$\delta_I^2(H, \theta) = \exp \left[\frac{0.49 \delta_{Ry}^2(H, \theta)}{(1 + 1.11 \delta_{Ry}^{12/15}(H, \theta))^{7/6}} + \frac{0.51 \delta_{Ry}^2(H, \theta)}{(1 + 0.69 \delta_{Ry}^{12/15}(H, \theta))^{5/6}} \right] - 1, \quad (8)$$

where,

$$\delta_{Ry}^2(H, \theta) = 2.25 k^{7/6} sec^{11/6}(90 - \theta) \int_{h_0}^H dh' (h' - h_0)^{5/6} C_n^2(h').$$

The variation of the values of the scintillation index as the satellite is at different elevation angles is shown in Fig. 4a. After obtaining the value of the scintillation index, the values of α and β parameters can be computed by:

$$\alpha = \left[\exp \left(\frac{0.49 \delta^2}{(1 + 1.11 \delta^{12/15})^{7/6}} \right) - 1 \right]^{-1} \quad (9)$$

$$\beta = \left[\exp \left(\frac{0.51 \delta^2}{(1 + 0.69 \delta^{12/15})^{7/6}} \right) - 1 \right]^{-1}. \quad (10)$$

Ultimately, the values of α and β can be substituted to (6) to obtain the $pdf(I|H, \theta)$, i.e., the PDF of the irradiance, I , of a satellite link with an altitude, H , at an elevation angle, θ . In Fig. 4b, the PDF of the irradiance at $20^\circ \leq \theta \leq 80^\circ$ is shown. To obtain a single PDF that would represent the entire free-space optic channel, we performed convolution for all the resulting PDF, and it is shown in Fig. 4c.

B. Radio Frequency Channel

For the RF link, the received signals can be expressed as:

$$y_{RF}(t) = \sqrt{E_s} h_{RF}(t) x_{RF}(t) + n_{RF}(t), \quad (11)$$

where E_s is the symbol energy, $h_{RF}(t)$ is the fading, and $n_{RF}(t)$ is the RF Gaussian noise. The fading are loss in the amplitude of the original signal as it propagates from the transmitter to the receiver.

For an ideal satellite downlink with no obstruction, the majority of the signal received is from the Line-of-Sight

(a) Scintillation index across different elevation angles

(b) Probability distribution of optical irradiance across all elevation angles

(c) Unified probability distribution of optical irradiance

Fig. 4: Characterization of the free-space optic channel between Earth and satellite

(a) Rician K-factor and sigma across different elevation angles

(b) Probability distribution of Rician fading across all elevation angles

(c) Unified probability distribution of Rician fading

Fig. 5: Characterization of the radio frequency channel between Earth and satellite

(LoS) component, while the others are from the non-Line-of-Sight (nLoS) or reflected components, also referred to as the multipath. For this scenario, the probability of the fading can be modelled using the Ricean distribution and its pdf can be expressed as [13]:

$$p(h_{RF}) = \frac{h_{RF}}{\sigma^2} \cdot e^{-K - \frac{h_{RF}}{\sigma^2}} + I_0\left(2h_{RF}\sqrt{\frac{K}{2\sigma^2}}\right), h_{RF} \geq 0, \quad (12)$$

where K is the vanishing factor or K -factor, σ^2 is the average power of the reflected components, and $I_0(\cdot)$ is the modified Bessel function of the first kind. The K -factor is an important parameter in Ricean distribution as it describes how much of the received signal is from the LoS and the multipath components respectively. In other words, it is the ratio between the average power of the LoS component, $a^2/2$, and the average power of the multipath component, σ^2 , thus, $K = a^2/2\sigma^2$. A very large value of K , $K \rightarrow \infty$, suggests that the LoS component in the received is very strong and very few reflections, while, a very small value of K , $K \rightarrow 0$, suggests that the LoS component of blocked, and majority of the received signal is from the multipath component.

In the case of non-stationary satellites such as LEO, the values of K -factor and σ^2 change as they travel along its path. Therefore, their relationship with the elevation angle should be established. There is no direct way to compute these values,

but data fitting based on data collected can be used to derive them. According to the report provided in [14], by using the data collected from ESA of various values of K -factor and σ at different elevation angles, these empirical formulas are established for $20^\circ \leq \theta \leq 80^\circ$:

$$K(\theta) = K_0 + K_1(\theta) + K_2(\theta^2), \quad (13)$$

$$\sigma(\theta) = \sigma_0 + \sigma_1(\theta), \quad (14)$$

where, $K_0 = 2.731$, $K_1 = -1.074 \times 10^{-1}$, $K_2 = 2.774 \times 10^{-9}$, $\sigma_0 = 4.5$, and $\sigma_1 = -0.05$. These relationships are shown in Fig. 5a. Similar to FSO, all the PDF of the Rician fading, and its resulting convolution are shown in Fig. 5b and Fig. 5c, respectively.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section presents the numerical results of the BER performance of the proposed system, as well as its spectral efficiency in terms of the cumulative distribution function of the throughput, while considering the channel impairments introduced as the RF and FSO signals with equal SNR propagate through the atmosphere. Here, a numerical simulation of a zenith-crossing LEO satellite with an altitude $H = 600$ km, operating at optical wavelength $\lambda = 1060$ nm, radio frequency $f_r = 40$ GHz, and a receiving ground station with a height $h_0 = 30$ m, is performed.

Fig. 6: Average BER with Channel Impairments, $SNR_{RF} = SNR_{FSO}$

Fig. 8: Cumulative Distribution Function of the Throughput, $SNR_{RF} - 15dB = SNR_{FSO}$

Fig. 7: Average BER on 16-QAM ($N = 4$) and 256-QAM ($N = 8$)

Fig. 9: Average Throughput on 16-QAM ($N = 4$) and 256-QAM ($N = 8$)

In Fig. 6, it can be observed the BER values considering the proposed channel models. It can be noticed that without any techniques, the FSO-only link performs the weakest, as it endures channel impairments and additive noise. The MRC system provides an improvement as the combination of the RF and FSO links reduces the errors caused by their respective impairments, which would optimize the demodulation process. Overall, our proposed Modified Hierarchical Modulation shows the best improvement and is the most robust against noise and impairments. It is because compared to the other techniques, the modulation index used to modulate the RF and FSO signals respectively are lower, owing to the fact that the HP and LP streams are the compartmentalized components of the original data block. Furthermore, since the HP stream is transmitted via RF link, under the assumption that RF is more robust than the FSO, the probability of error that the LP stream will land on the wrong quadrant is very low, thus, making the demapping process less erroneous. To check the performance at different modulation orders, the proposed

technique is performed on lower and higher modulation level, 16-QAM and 256-QAM respectively. Fig. 7 shows that MHH still performs the best among the other schemes.

In Fig. 8, multiple iterations are performed to numerically evaluate the cumulative density function of the throughput. In this simulation, we have considered a SNR gap between RF and FSO of 15 dBs. MHH appears to have a larger gain for the percentile 0.01, providing a sufficiently large data rate compared to FSO-only and MRC. Considering the average throughput over different SNR values, the results shown in Fig. 9 support that the proposed scheme outperforms the benchmark techniques.

And lastly, in Table. I, we analyze the throughput of the systems when varying this SNR gap between the two links. Here, the scenario described is when the FSO is the one suffering from larger noise and channel impairments. It can be noticed that in all cases, MHH has better gain than in MRC. At equal SNR, 0 dB, a guaranteed 14.9% gain can be expected for MHH, and as the gap increases.

TABLE I: Throughput Gain at Different SNR Gaps

SNR Gap (dB)	Benchmark (bps/Hz)	MRC (bps/Hz)	Gain (%)	MHM (bps/Hz)	Gain (%)
0 dB	3.83	4.15	8.4	4.40	14.9
5 dB	3.44	3.79	10.2	4.07	18.3
12 dB	3.17	3.36	6	3.85	21.5
15 dB	3.12	3.24	3.8	3.78	21.5
20 dB	3.06	3.15	2.9	3.72	21.6

V. CONCLUSION

This paper proposed the MHM technique for a Satellite Hybrid RF-FSO system, where the bit streams are segmented, prioritized and transmitted simultaneously over the RF and FSO links, where the RF symbols are the a priori information of the FSO symbols. In an AWGN channel, our numerical results show that in comparison to typically utilized combining schemes implemented for a Hybrid RF-FSO system such as MRC scheme, MHM performs better in terms of BER and throughput, when transmitting the same number of bits on equal SNR conditions. Similarly, in a non-stationary satellite forward link transmission, considering the effects of the atmospheric channel, irradiance for the FSO part, and fading for the RF part; our numerical results show that our proposed system performs well in terms of its BER and throughput, and better compared to MRC technique.

In spite of outperforming MRC on different SNR conditions, the authors do not consider the use of these three systems to be mutually exclusive, thus, future works can be considered to harness the benefits of the three, where intelligent adaptive switching techniques when a pre-defined SNR threshold is reached can be implemented.

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